

Agricultural Credit Programmes and Economic Growth: Evidence From Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between agricultural credit programmes and economic growth in Nigeria, using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach with annual data from 1987 to 2021. Data were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the World Development Indicators database. The primary aim was to assess the impact of crop production, food production, and livestock production on Nigeria's economic growth. After conducting several empirical tests, the results confirmed a short-term link between food production, livestock production, and economic growth. They also show that all explanatory variables collectively account for short-term fluctuations in Nigeria's economic growth. Further analysis of the ARDL short-term estimates indicated that changes in crop production and livestock production during the current and previous periods had a positive effect on Nigeria's short-term economic growth. Conversely, variations in food production during the current and previous periods had a negative impact on economic growth. The study concludes that a significant long-term relationship exists between agricultural production and Nigeria's economic growth. Therefore, it recommends that the government implement sound macroeconomic policies to maximise the benefits of the agricultural sector and promote economic growth in Nigeria.

Keywords: Economic growth, Agricultural finance, Output, GDP, Agricultural production

Introduction

There is no denying that agriculture is a vital tool for boosting the economic growth and development of many countries worldwide. Its role in any economy is undeniably significant and cannot be ignored. The agricultural sector is essential for achieving long-term economic progress (Ugah, 2020). Ayeomoni and Aladejana (2016), as cited in IFAD (2001), stated that agriculture is the leading employer of labour and a major contributor to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in most African nations. Developing countries have experienced notable economic and agricultural growth, thanks to the combined efforts of governments and private financial institutions providing credit to farmers and agricultural businesses. Agricultural credit plays a crucial role in supporting production and economic development (Langwenya, 2019). It involves providing financial resources, such as loans and credit facilities, to farmers and stakeholders in the agricultural sector.

Access to credit facilities for agricultural producers and agribusinesses has become increasingly difficult, hampering the country's agricultural potential and restricting sector growth. That is why, in the 1970s, the Nigerian government introduced policies and initiatives to attract financing and boost agricultural production. In Nigeria, agricultural credit programmes are designed to provide financial support to farmers and agricultural enterprises, playing a crucial role in shaping agricultural output in various ways. For example, offering financial assistance to farmers and agriculturists enables them to purchase seedlings, fertilisers, and machinery, thus increasing their productivity. Additionally, agricultural credit allows farmers to access advanced agricultural technologies, which subsequently lead to higher yields. Moreover, Temsas et al. (2021) highlighted that agricultural credit programmes serve as a safety net, helping farmers manage and mitigate risks associated with losses and continue their production activities.

Agricultural credit can encourage crop diversification, resulting in higher agricultural productivity. In addition to supporting crop production, agricultural credit programmes can also assist livestock farming by enabling farmers to invest in superior animal breeds and veterinary services, which in turn boosts livestock productivity. Historically in Nigeria, during the pre- and immediate post-independence periods, agricultural production driven by credit programmes and policy reforms not only benefited farmers but also contributed significantly to economic growth, accounting for over 80 percent of the nation's GDP (CBN, 2021). It invigorates local economies, generates income for rural communities, and enhances citizens' living standards. However, it is important to recognise that the positive effects of agricultural credit programmes on economic development depend on several factors. These include, but are not limited to, sector neglect, high interest rates, improper credit utilisation by farmers, limited access to modern inputs and technology, and inadequate credit supply (Vogel, 2013).

Recognising the importance of the agricultural sector, successive governments have developed and implemented various agricultural credit programmes to ensure the availability and accessibility of funds that support the sector's growth. These initiatives aim to promote real sector advancement in pursuit of economic growth and development. Such financial schemes include, but are not limited to, the creation of the Nigerian Agricultural Cooperative Bank (NACB) in 1973, the establishment of the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) in 1977, the introduction of mandatory sectoral allocation to agriculture in 1972, the launch of the Rural Banking Scheme in 1977, the setting up of the Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme in 2009, the launch of the Agricultural Credit Support Scheme (ACSS), and the merger of NACB, the People's Bank, and the Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP) to form the Nigerian Agricultural Cooperative and Rural Development Bank (NACRDB) in 2000. Others include the introduction of differential interest rates on loans for agricultural activities by the Central Bank of Nigeria, the establishment of agricultural research institutes, increased budgetary allocations to the sector, and the provision of subsidies to farmers for agricultural inputs.

Many policies and programmes have been created to improve the flow of credit to farmers, helping them to mechanise and boost their agricultural activities. This should ultimately improve food security, raise farmers' incomes, supply vital raw materials for local agro-based industries, decrease the import of agricultural products, and above all, contribute substantially to the nation's GDP. To meet these objectives, the CBN has issued directives to commercial banks, which are among the financial institutions responsible for mobilising credit to the agricultural sector. Despite the presence of numerous financial institutions, farmers' credit demands are frequently unmet. In many cases where banks do provide funds, delays in disbursing approved loans pose a challenge. Often, these loans arrive after the planting season, leading to diversion and subsequent default. Due to the high default rate on loans in developing countries, commercial banks rarely approve loans to farmers and often do so at higher interest rates with strict conditions, such as collateral (Basse, 2014). Supporting this, Shekhar and Shekhar (2005) stated that commercial banks are discouraged from focusing on the agricultural sector because of the economic nature of land holdings, the limited resources of most rural farmers, and the lack of acceptable collateral securities. The extent and severity of this credit shortage have considerably impacted farmers and weakened productivity in the sector over the years.

Additionally, a large proportion of farmers, especially in rural areas, remain impoverished, and this situation worsens due to declining productivity and rising income inequality. The income inequality coefficient stands at 0.49 in rural areas and 0.54 in urban areas (MDGs Report, 2005). Furthermore, the rapid increase in imports of certain agricultural products—once the main components of Nigeria's exports, mainly produced by smallholder farmers—continues despite the availability of credit facilities. In 2003 alone, Nigeria imported over 183,000 metric tons of palm oil, 95,000 metric tons of cotton, and

431,000 metric tons of maize. Before the rice import ban, Nigeria was spending an average of \$60 million annually on rice imports (Bernard, 2007).

All efforts to promote economic growth through agricultural credit programmes over the years have not led to significant progress. This situation is worsened by agricultural credit policies and programmes designed to enhance the sector, which also benefit other parts of the economy—for example, by supplying raw materials. It is hoped that Nigeria will eventually experience economic growth, higher food production, increased livestock and crop yields, along with higher per capita income and reductions in poverty and income inequality. However, these aspirations have remained unfulfilled for years. Furthermore, many agro-industries are underperforming in productivity, with some closing due to a lack of essential raw materials needed for production. It is evident that agricultural production, particularly food, is both an economic and political issue in Nigeria today. The recent challenges caused by high food costs are closely linked to the overall health of the economy because of their negative effects. These issues concern not only the government, which prefers a modest increase in food prices, but also consumers, whose incomes are strained by high food prices. As a result, it is vital to investigate the factors responsible for this. Moreover, any economy that cannot supply its citizens with sufficient food and support for its agro-industries becomes unstable, hindering economic growth and development. Additionally, research that highlights and offers solutions to these issues remains limited. In light of this, the study aims to examine the impact of agricultural credit programmes on crop, food, and livestock production, as well as their influence on Nigeria's economic growth from 1987 to 2021.

Review of Literature and Theoretical Framework

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Agriculture maintains a vital role in an economy; without it, a country will consistently depend on foreign nations to feed its population. The potential contribution of agriculture in stimulating economic growth has long been debated among development economists. Many scholars contend that overall economic growth relies on the development of the agricultural sector (Gollin, Parente, and Rogerson 2002). Growth in the agricultural sector is undeniably a central factor in national output expansion, as it affects rural incomes and supplies resources for transforming into an industrialised economy (Thirtle, Lin, and Piesse 2003).

Rhaji (2008), as cited in Johnston and Mellor (1961), stated that agriculture contributes to economic growth and development through five inter-sectoral linkages. These linkages include the supply of surplus labour to firms in the industrial sector, the provision of food for domestic consumption, the creation of markets for industrial output, the supply of domestic savings and industrial investment, and the export of agricultural products to earn foreign exchange for importing intermediate and capital goods. Additionally, Timmer (1995) observed that agriculture indirectly supports economic growth by improving caloric nutrient intake among the poor, ensuring food availability, stabilising food prices, and reducing poverty.

A credit facility serves as the essential starting point for any transaction, especially in agriculture, which is often seen as a non-monetary activity for rural populations in developing nations. This sector's success relies heavily on credit support due to seasonal fluctuations in farmers' income. As a result, providing access to credit is the fastest way to increase agricultural output (Akinleye, Akanni, & Oladoja, 2005). Studies indicate that agricultural credit is vital for sector development, especially in Nigeria; in fact, the economic downturn is partly due to farmers' limited access to credit facilities, particularly those adopting mechanisation (Beck & Honohan, 2008).

Shreiner and Yaron (2001) define agricultural credit as resources, whether public or private, in the form of equity, gifts, or loans, aimed at improving social welfare through the development of the agricultural sector. It includes not only government funds but also funds from non-governmental organisations that use matching grants to promote community and sector development, income equality, and local empowerment. They argue that public funds are subsidised, and private funds are considered so regardless of their cost, unless a contribution is tax-free or an explicit or implicit government guarantee of the liabilities of a development finance institution influences the market price.

Agricultural credit can be defined as the mobilisation of resources at all levels to increase production and productivity in agriculture and to enhance productive capacity. Agricultural credit in an emerging economy can have a positive impact on the country's gross domestic product growth, ultimately benefiting the entire economy. Agriculture credit or finance promotes growth and addresses the challenges that hinder the productivity of the agriculture sector. It serves as an effective engine for growth in many agriculture-based countries (ADB, 2000). Over the years, agricultural credit has been recognised as a key component for revitalising the agricultural sector and as a driving force for the growth of other non-agricultural sectors in Nigeria (Chebbi & Lassad, 2007; Ezeokeke, Anyanwu, & Okoro, 2012; Rehman, 2016).

A credit facility enhances the potential for improving productivity thresholds, revenue efficiency, and living standards (Ayeomoni & Aladejana, 2016). Building on this idea, the Malaysian government founded Agro Bank, formerly known as Bank Pertanian Malaysia, to offer financial backing for agricultural activities and diversify into new business sectors. Similarly, India has comparable agricultural credit schemes, including programmes for financing sericulture, apiculture (beekeeping), and fisheries development, among others (PNB, 2016).

Los and Gardbroek (2015), in their study of fifty-two (52) African countries from 1961 to 2010, identified that agriculture plays different roles at various stages of economic growth. To reach this conclusion, they employed a range of variables, including agricultural output, agricultural labour, institutional quality, agricultural technology, productivity growth using total factor productivity as a proxy for 'productivity growth,' the food production index, malnutrition, and economic growth measured by GDP as the dependent variable in one of their models.

Agriculture financing is fundamentally a development strategy in many respects. It promotes agricultural investment and the adoption of technology essential for driving economic growth. Although agriculture finance is only one of the growth factors, it is among the more significant ones for achieving development objectives. Chenery and Strout (1966) assume that there is an excess supply of labour and that growth is solely limited by the availability and productivity of capital in developing countries. Therefore, it is clear that agricultural growth has historically played a vital role in economic development; evidence from both industrialised nations and rapidly developing countries today demonstrates that the sector has been the engine that contributes to overall economic growth.

Theoretical Framework

This section presents the theoretical framework linking the variables, particularly the connection between agricultural credit programs and Nigeria's economic growth, as measured by real gross domestic product. The study uses classical growth theory and the theory of financial intermediation.

Levi's Classical growth theory

Classical theorists, led by Arthur Lewis in the 1950s, regarded economic development as a process of relocating factors of production, especially labour, from an agricultural sector with low productivity

and traditional technology to a modern industrial sector with higher productivity and advanced technology. The role of agriculture in development was limited, mainly serving as a source of food and labour rather than as a driver of growth. Although passive, agricultural development was considered vital for a successful economic revolution, primarily to maintain a stable food supply and prevent rising food prices and real wages from impeding industrial growth. It also aimed to utilise land as an additional source of growth that would not compete with resources needed for industrial development.

Ruttan (2000) argued that agriculture's role in driving overall economic growth can be understood through its impact on total factor productivity or as a transitional input in the industrial production sector. Early development theories regarded agriculture as a vital source of resources to finance the expansion of the industrial sector. Consequently, growth in agricultural production acts as a catalyst for economic development. Considering agriculture as the foundation of growth, Hwa (1988) incorporated agriculture into the well-known Solow-Swan growth equation as a way to measure the links between the rural and industrial sectors of the economy.

Theory of financial intermediation

Credit is an essential aspect of financial intermediation because it supplies funds to those economic entities that can utilise them most effectively. Theoretical research has confirmed the link between financial intermediation and economic growth. Schumpeter (1934), Goldsmith (1969), McKinnon (1973), and Shaw (1973) have emphasised the importance of financial intermediation in fostering economic development. Likewise, Greenwood and Jovanovich (1990) noted that financial development can lead to quicker growth.

In a related study, Bencivenga and Smith (1991) explained that the development of banks and efficient financial intermediation contribute to economic growth by channeling savings into high-productivity activities such as agriculture and by reducing liquidity risks. They therefore concluded that financial intermediation leads to growth.

Based on this assertion, with the agricultural sector as a deficit unit, this study examines how credit programmes for the agricultural sector have influenced economic growth in Nigeria. This suggests that financial institutions can promote economic growth by effectively executing their functions, including providing more favourable credit to the agricultural sector. Building on these theories, we propose that loans and grants supporting credit programmes in Nigeria should largely help boost food production in the country, increase agricultural output, improve the institutional quality of agricultural products, enhance the technology used in the sector, mobilise labour for the sector, and improve access to funds for sector players. This, in turn, will lead to significant economic growth.

Empirical Review

Numerous studies examine how agricultural credit programmes influence economic growth. Temsas et al. (2021) used data from 1998 to 2020 and an ARDL model to find that agricultural credit, human capital, life expectancy, and foreign direct investment positively impact long-term economic development. However, FDI has a short-term adverse effect. Life expectancy and currency devaluation support growth, with rapid adjustments indicated by a significant error correction term, confirming a long-run equilibrium between variables. There is bidirectional causality between bank agricultural credits and HDI. Ayeomoni and Aladejana (2016) studied Nigeria (1986-2014) and found that agricultural credit and variables such as the real exchange rate and private domestic investment directly influence growth, while inflation negatively affects it. Their findings suggest Nigeria's growth depends on factors like credit to agriculture, the exchange rate, interest rates, investment, and inflation, highlighting the need for policies that improve agricultural productivity through adequate credit.

Okosodo (2016) investigated agricultural credit and its influence on the growth and development of the Nigerian economy. The study analysed banking policies related to agricultural credit development in Nigeria from 1980 to 2014. The data primarily came from secondary sources. The research utilised recent bounds testing cointegration, unit root tests, and an error correction mechanism. The findings indicated a long-term relationship between the agricultural sector and economic growth in Nigeria. It also demonstrated that government expenditure on agriculture contributed modestly to the country's economic growth. Therefore, it is recommended that the federal government encourage commercial banks to offer sufficient credit facilities to the agricultural sector and reduce the bank lending rate to motivate more Nigerian farmers.

Udoka, Mbat, and Duke (2016) examined the impact of commercial banks' credit on Nigeria's agricultural output from 1970 to 2013. Using OLS regression on data from the CBN bulletin, they found a positive and significant link between the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund and output, suggesting that increased scheme funding boosts production. They also identified a positive relationship between bank credit and agricultural output, indicating that increased bank lending leads to higher production. The study highlighted that government agricultural expenditure positively affects output, while higher interest rates negatively impact it by discouraging borrowing. The authors recommended proper funding of the scheme and government guarantees to encourage more lending and sustain growth.

Nnamocha and Eke (2015) examined the effect of bank credit on Nigeria's agricultural output using the Error Correction Model (ECM). Analysing annual data from 1970 to 2013 from the Central Bank of Nigeria, they found all variables were I(1) and shared a long-term relationship. The results indicated that, in the long run, bank credit and industrial output significantly enhanced agriculture, while only industrial output had a short-term effect on agriculture. They recommended that the government implement policies to make bank credit more accessible to support agricultural growth and employment. The study emphasised the vital role of the industrial sector in agriculture, as it supplies raw materials to industry, which in turn promotes agricultural development, demonstrating a reciprocal relationship.

Obansa and Maduekwe (2013) examined the effect of agriculture financing on Nigeria's economic growth. Using secondary data and econometric methods such as OLS, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test, and the Granger Causality test, the results from various models showed bidirectional causality between economic growth and agricultural financing. This indicates a two-way relationship between economic growth and agricultural expansion. It also suggests that investment productivity is most effectively financed through foreign direct private loans, share capital, foreign direct investment, and development stocks. Furthermore, the capital-output ratio is better funded through multilateral loans, domestic savings, treasury bills, official development assistance, foreign direct investment, and development stocks. They recommended maintaining credible, pro-investment macroeconomic policies, as well as considering debt-equity swaps, to foster an agricultural-led economic growth.

Nzomo and Muturi (2014) examined how agricultural credit programs affect the productivity of rural households in Kimilili, Bungoma Sub-County. They used a cross-sectional survey with a structured questionnaire to collect data from 123 randomly chosen small-scale farmers who use micro-credit. Their findings suggest that agricultural credit can boost farmers' incomes by over 100%, emphasising the significant role of credit in agriculture. They recommended that the government offer attractive incentives to encourage increased production among smallholder farmers and should also provide "soft loans" on very favorable terms.

Nwankwo (2013) examined agricultural financing in Nigeria and its implications for the growth of the Nigerian economy using ordinary least squares and a quantitative research design. The study observed a significant relationship between agricultural financing and the growth of the Nigerian economy, and that the loan repayment rate over the years has had a negative impact on economic growth. The results have important policy implications for promoting economic growth through agricultural financing. The study therefore recommends increasing the level and size of NACRDB agricultural loans by reducing interest rates to foster more economic development in the country, especially considering the long-term relationship between Nigeria's Agricultural Cooperative and Rural Development Bank's agricultural financing and economic growth.

Oji-Okoro (2011) examined the impact of the agricultural sector on the Nigerian economy. The panel data used were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria's statistical bulletin and the World Bank's development indicators. Multiple regression was used to analyse the data. The results indicated a positive relationship between Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and domestic savings, government expenditure on agriculture, and foreign direct investment during the period from 1986 to 2007. The study also revealed that 81% of the variation in GDP could be attributed to domestic savings, government expenditure, and foreign direct investment. To improve the agricultural sector, it was recommended that the government provide more funding for agricultural universities in Nigeria to conduct research across all areas of agricultural production, which will lead to increased exports and improved competitiveness of Nigerian agricultural products in international markets. The CBN should also develop a stable policy for loan disbursement to farmers at reasonable interest rates.

Nwachukwu et al. (2008) examined the impact of Nigerian government expenditure on agricultural output using the ordinary least squares (OLS) estimation technique for the period 1977-2006. The results show that agricultural output does not respond significantly to government expenditure on agriculture. It confirms that the government's contribution to agricultural development is insufficient. The study thus suggested that the unique role of agriculture be recognised so that the sector can receive its fair share of government expenditure.

Iganiga and Unemhilin (2011) conducted a study on the impact of government agricultural expenditure and other factors on the value of Nigerian agricultural output. They specified the Cobb-Douglas growth model to include food imports, annual average rainfall, commercial credit to agriculture, GDP growth rate, consumer price index, and population growth rate. The error correction results revealed a positive relationship between government capital expenditure and agricultural output.

The literature review indicates that no studies have been conducted to evaluate the impact of different agricultural credit programs on Nigeria's economic growth through their intended channels. This study aims to fill this gap by analysing each of the identified agricultural credit program variables separately, including sector budget allocations, agricultural subsidies for farm inputs and supplements, the food production index, and other relevant factors.

Methodology

The research method aims to evaluate the relationship between agricultural credit programs in Nigeria and economic growth. We employ the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach to cointegration, as described by Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001) and adapted by Ayeomoni and Aladejana (2016). The advantages of the ARDL model include its ability to be used with individual regressors regardless of whether they are integrated of order $I(0)$ or $I(1)$, without regard to stationarity. The model takes enough lags to effectively capture the data generation process within a general-to-specific

modeling framework. It provides more accurate estimates of long-term coefficients, and the diagnostic tests of the estimated equation are more reliable. From the ARDL model, a dynamic error correction model (ECM) can be easily derived through a simple linear transformation. The ECM helps us understand the short-term relationships among the variables. Lastly, the ARDL model is more suitable for smaller sample sizes. Given that our study has only 60 observations, this approach is particularly appropriate for our analysis. The data were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, various issues, the World Bank data site via the internet, and journals, spanning the period from 1987 to 2021.

Model specification and technique of analysis

For this research, the study aims to define the model below based on the assumption that economic growth is a function of credit to agriculture. In functional form, equation (1) is expressed as:

$$RGDP = f(CPPROD, FDPROD, LSPROD) \text{ ----- (1)}$$

In econometric terms, equation (2) is restated in its log form as follows:

$$LRGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1LCPPRODt + \beta_2LFDPROD + \beta_3LLSPRODt + Ut \text{ ----- (2)}$$

Where: RGDP is real gross domestic product, a proxy for economic growth.

CPPROD is the crop production index.

FDPROD is the food production index.

LSPROD is the livestock production index

L = represents the log of the dependent and independent variables, where Ut = random error and t = period, respectively.

We estimate both the short-term and long-term relationships between the variables in the model using the ARDL approach. Hence, equation (3) is specified as follows:

$$RGDP = \beta_0 + \sum\beta_1CPPRODt_{-1} + \sum\beta_2FDPROD_{t-1} + \sum\beta_3LSPROD_{t-1} + Ut \text{ ----- (3)}$$

Where β_0 is the drift component and \sum is the summation sign (sigma), which represents the error correction, the first part of the equation corresponds to the short-run relationship. In contrast, the second part, represented by γ , represents the long-run relationship.

Based on the literature reviewed, positive relationships with economic growth are expected from the independent variables of CPPROD, FDPROD, and LSPROD.

Results and Discussions

Table 1: Result of descriptive statistical analysis

	RGDP	CPPROD	FDPROD	LSPROD
Mean	4.614857	73.89000	73.95657	80.59829
Median	4.210000	74.47000	76.29000	85.91000
Maximum	14.60000	112.6200	111.7400	103.8200
Minimum	-1.790000	28.87000	30.52000	49.54000
Std. Dev.	3.852939	23.56380	23.30487	19.33111

Skewness	0.477938	-0.076910	-0.093647	-0.432705
Kurtosis	2.760145	2.068975	2.012012	1.677947
Jarque-Bera	1.416375	1.298599	1.474664	3.641106
Probability	0.492536	0.022412	0.478389	0.161936
Observations	35	35	35	35

Source: E-view 12.0 statistical software

Descriptive analysis

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the data used in this study. The results show that real gross domestic product (RGDP) has a mean value of 4.614857, with a standard deviation of 3.852939, ranging from -1.79000 to 14.6000 as the minimum and maximum values. Agricultural crop production (CPPROD) has a minimum value of 28.87000 and a maximum of 112.6200, with an average value of 73.89000 and a standard deviation of 23.56380, respectively.

The descriptive statistics analysis also revealed that agricultural food production (FDPROD) has its lowest value at 30.52000 and its highest at 111.7400. Its mean value was 73.95657, while its standard deviation was 23.30487. Lastly, agricultural livestock production (LSPROD) has an average value of 80.59829, with a standard deviation of 19.33111, ranging from 49.54000 to 103.8200 as the minimum and maximum values.

The descriptive statistics analysis further indicated that the measurement of skewness showed that only the RGDP variable is rightly skewed (positively skewed). In contrast, variables such as CPPROD, FDPROD, and LSPROD were negatively skewed (leftward skewed). The kurtosis coefficients of the variables suggest that all variables, including RGDP, CPPROD, FDPROD, and LSPROD, were flat (platykurtic or below 3.000), indicating a deviation from a normal distribution. The Jarque-Bera (JB) test measures the difference in skewness and kurtosis between the series and those of a normal distribution. The JB value of 1.298599 for the CPROD variable, along with its corresponding probability of less than 0.05%, confirms the series' normality and its suitability for generalisation. It indicates the absence of outliers in the data.

VAR lag criteria

Since the unit root test is sensitive to lag length, we use the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Schwarz Information Criterion (SC), and Hannan-Quinn Information Criterion (HQ) to select the appropriate criterion. Both AIC and HQ unanimously suggest a lag length of 3, while SC recommends a lag of 1. Therefore, the study adopts the AIC with lag length 3, which has the lowest criterion value in its model estimation.

Table 2: VAR lag order selection criteria

Included observations: 35

Lag formation	AIC	SC	HQ
0	15.12522	15.12522	15.17077
1	9.721559	10.27121*	9.093753
2	9.526749	10.48864	9.845588
3	9.244992*	10.61912	9.700477*

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion (tested at 5% level each)

Source: E-views 12.0 statistical software

Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test is used to determine whether a time series is stationary. The primary purpose of this test is to determine whether the variables in the model are

suitable and whether they lack a unit root. Since most time series data are not stationary, conducting a unit root test on the data is important. This study employed the ADF test to verify the stationarity of the data and the order of integration. To determine if the time series is stationary, the ADF test statistic values must be greater than the MacKinnon critical values at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels, with comparison made on the absolute value. The results of the ADF test are shown in Table 2.

The analysis of the ADF unit root test revealed that none of the variables of interest in this study was found to be stationary at levels; therefore, it becomes impossible at this stage to reject their null hypotheses since the test statistic values at level for each variable using the ADF unit root test statistics were below the critical values at one percent, five percent, and ten percent levels of significance. However, once all the variables were differenced, they became stationary. This is because the ADF unit root test statistic values were found to be greater than the critical values at the conventional one per cent, five per cent, and ten per cent levels of significance, indicating that all the variables of interest had the same order of integration I (1).

Table 3: Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test

Variables	At Level	At 1 st Difference	Order of integration	Significant at 0.05
RGDP	-2.7079	-4.8587***	I(0)	0.0005
CPPROD	-0.5883	-3.7756***	I(1)	0.0077
FDPROD	-0.7139	-3.6628***	I(1)	0.0102
LSPROD	-1.8521	-5.6273***	I(1)	0.0000
TEST OF CRITICAL VALUES: 1%, 5%, 10%				

Source: E-view 12.0 statistical software

Stability test

The result of the CUSUM test, as shown in Figure 1, indicates that all plots fall within the two straight lines, indicating that the ARDL model is stable.

Figure 1: CUSUM stability test

ARDL F-bound testing approach

The F-test using the Wald test (bound test) is conducted to examine the overall significance of the coefficients specified in the model. The Wald test is performed by imposing restrictions on the estimated long-run coefficients of agricultural production variables (CPPROD, FDPROD, LSPROD) and the

growth of the Nigerian economy (RGDP). The ARDL F-bound test, with lower and upper bounds tabulated, is selected based on a five percent significance level.

Table 4: ARDL F-bounds test

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No level relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
			Asymptotic: n=1000	
F-statistic	6.319883	10%	2.37	3.2
K	3	5%	2.79	3.67
		2.5%	3.15	4.08
		1%	3.65	4.66
Actual Sample Size	33		Finite Sample: n=35	
		10%	2.618	3.532
		5%	3.164	4.194
		1%	4.428	5.816
			Finite Sample: n=30	
		10%	2.676	3.586
		5%	3.272	4.306
		1%	4.614	5.966

Source: E-views 12.0 statistical software

However, this study is based on the conventional five percent significance level. Therefore, the results in Table 3 show that the agricultural production variables (CPPROD, FDPROD, LSPROD) are jointly co-integrated with the dependent variable, RGDP, indicating the existence of a long-term relationship. The calculated F-statistic is 6.31 at the 5% significance level and is greater than both the ARDL lower (2.79) and upper (3.67) critical bound values. This demonstrates evidence of long-run co-integration between agricultural production variables (CPPROD, FDPROD, LSPROD) and the growth of the Nigerian economy (RGDP).

Table 5: ARDL long-run form

Dependent Variable: D(RGDP)				
Selected Model: ARDL (1, 0, 2, 1)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(FPPROD)	-3.988890	0.655469	-6.085552	0.0000
(FDPROD(-1))	0.212974	1.970473	1.970473	0.0300
(LSPROD)	0.397242	2.706137	2.706137	0.0121
CntEq(-1)	-0.816018	-6.054364	-6.054364	0.0000
R-squared	0.562862	DW stats		2.066670
Adjusted R-squared	0.517640			

Source: E-views 12.0 statistical software

ARDL long-run form estimates

Regarding the unit root test for the order of integration, ‘I(0)’ and ‘I(1)’, this study aims to confirm the possibility of long-run cointegration among variables of the same order of integration. Based on the ARDL bound test results, it is concluded that a long-run relationship exists among the variables in the model. Therefore, there is a need to estimate the long-run coefficients, which measure the long-term effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

From the ARDL long-run form in Table 5, long-run estimates showed that the independent variables (FDPROD(-1), LSPROD) have a jointly significant positive effect on economic growth in Nigeria over the long term. This suggests that an increase in these variables will have a positive impact on Nigeria's long-term economic growth. However, the relationship between FDPROD and the growth of the Nigerian economy in the current period was found to be negative but significant. The result of the error correction term (CointEq (-1)*) had an estimated coefficient of -0.81. The result was highly statistically significant, indicating that deviations from the equilibrium path in the model are corrected by 0.81% annually.

Table 6: ARDL short-run dynamics result

Dependent Variable: LRGDP				
Selected Model: ARDL(1, 0, 2, 1)				
<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>t-Statistic</i>	<i>Prob. *</i>
RGDP(-1)	0.183982	0.163229	1.127140	0.2704
CPPROD	3.592243	2.554931	1.406004	0.1720
FDPROD	-3.988890	2.766013	-1.442108	0.1617
FDPROD(-1)	-0.084914	0.131933	-0.643616	0.5257
FDPROD(-2)	-0.212974	0.145708	-1.461652	0.1563
LSPROD	0.397242	0.318275	1.248108	0.2236
LSPROD(-1)	0.391817	0.177768	2.204098	0.0369
C	-8.537878	5.161135	-1.654264	0.1106
R-squared	0.624843	Mean dependent var		4.831818
Adjusted R-squared	0.519799	S.D. dependent var		3.857031
S.E. of regression	2.672789	Akaike info criterion		5.011339
Sum squared resid	178.5950	Schwarz criterion		5.374128
Log likelihood	-74.68709	Hannan-Quinn criterion.		5.133406
F-statistic	5.948397	Durbin-Watson stat		2.066670
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000378			
*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.				

Source: E-views 12.0 statistical software

ARDL short-run estimates

The ARDL short-run estimates presented in Table 6 indicate that the value of the intercept, at 8.5378, suggests that economic growth in Nigeria will decrease by 8.5378 per cent when all other variables are

held constant. The analysis also shows that the R-squared (R^2), which measures the overall goodness of fit of the entire ARDL model, has a value of 0.6248 (approximately 62.48%). This suggests that the independent variables (CPPROD, LSPROD, and LSPROD) explain about 62 percent of the variation in the dependent variable (RGDP).

Similarly, the high F-statistic value (5.9483) indicates that the overall model is statistically significant. The overall significance of the ARDL short-run model suggests that all explanatory variables collectively contribute to explaining the short-term fluctuations in Nigeria's economic growth.

Further analysis of the ARDL short-run estimates revealed that changes in the current period of CPPROD had a positive impact on Nigeria's economic growth. The implication is that a percentage increase in the crop production index will correspondingly boost Nigeria's economic growth in the short run, all else being equal.

The ARDL results further reveal that changes in the current period and the previous two lagged periods of FDPROD all harm the growth of the Nigerian economy. The implication is that a percentage increase in the food production index will decrease the growth of the Nigerian economy accordingly in the short run, all other things being equal.

Finally, further analysis of the ARDL short-run estimates showed that changes in both the current and previous lagged periods of LSPROD positively influenced the growth of the Nigerian economy. This suggests that, all else being equal, a percentage increase in the livestock production index will lead to a corresponding rise in Nigeria's economic growth in the short term.

ARDL error correction regression (ECT)

The results for the variables show that the expected negative sign of the error correction term (ECT) was highly significant. The highly significant ECT further confirms the existence of a stable and significant long-run relationship. This confirms the long-term significant relationship between agricultural production and the growth of the Nigerian economy, with its various lags. The coefficient of ECT (-0.81) shown in Table 6 indicates that deviations from long-term economic growth are corrected by approximately 81.60 per cent in the following year, all else being equal.

Conclusion and recommendations

This study primarily examined the relationship between agricultural credit programs and economic growth in Nigeria from 198 to 2021 using the ARDL approach. Data were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the World Development Indicators gazette. The findings confirmed the existence of a short-term relationship between food production, livestock production, and economic growth. The independent variables demonstrated a joint significance in explaining short-term changes in Nigeria's economic growth. This suggests that increases in these variables will have a significant impact on Nigeria's economic growth over time.

Further examination of the ARDL short-run estimates revealed that changes in the current period and the previous lagged period of CPPROD hurt economic growth in Nigeria. The implication is that a percentage increase in the crop production index will boost the growth of the Nigerian economy accordingly in the short run, all things being equal. On the other hand, the previous two, three, and four lagged periods of CPPROD were found to have a positive impact on the growth of the Nigerian economy.

The ARDL results further revealed that changes in both the current period and the previous lagged period of FDPROD have adverse effects on the growth of the Nigerian economy. The implication is that a percentage increase in the food production index will decrease Nigeria's economic growth accordingly in the short run, all other factors being equal. This could be due to overproduction, income inequality, resource depletion, trade imbalances, and other factors.

Lastly, further analysis of the ARDL short-run estimates showed that changes in both the current and previous lagged periods of LSPROD had a positive impact on the growth of the Nigerian economy. The implication is that a one per cent increase in the livestock production index will lead to a corresponding increase in Nigeria's economic growth in the short term, all other factors remaining constant.

In conclusion, the findings also suggest the need for reforms in both fiscal and monetary policies to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of credit utilisation in the agricultural sector, thereby enabling it to maximise its benefits. This can help increase agricultural output, generate more income, create employment opportunities, and also boost other sectors within and outside the economy. Essentially, effective management and monitoring of these key variables will undoubtedly promote economic growth in Nigeria.

The study therefore, suggested that

1. The government should develop policies aimed at diversifying the economy and encourage efforts to improve the non-oil sectors, especially agriculture.
2. Furthermore, due to the shortfall in agricultural output caused by inadequate credit financing from the government, the government should be more proactive in urging the private sector, particularly the financial sector, to allocate funds annually for agricultural financing to support government initiatives.
3. Additionally, the study revealed that even when funds are available, many farmers may be unaware of their existence. This lack of awareness hinders farmers' ability to access these funds and enhance agricultural productivity. Therefore, the government should use its agencies to educate farmers about the availability of such credit facilities.
4. Finally, there is a need to implement prudent macroeconomic policies to ensure the economy maximises benefits from the real sector, thereby promoting economic growth in Nigeria.

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